

Principles of Curriculum Development in an Effort to Improve Learning Quality

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ABSTRACT

One important component of the education system is the curriculum. The curriculum holds a key position in education, because it is related to the direction, content and process of education which eventually establishes the nature and credentials of an educational program's alumni institution. In this study the authors used library research methods. Curriculum development uses principles that have developed in everyday life or creates new principles. Therefore, in the implementation of the It is possible to utilize principles in curriculum in educational institutions that differ from those used in other educational institutions. so there will be many principles used in curriculum development

INTRODUCTION

One important component of the education system is the curriculum. The curriculum is a collection of plans and rules about the objectives, content, and learning materials and how they are used as guidelines for implementing learning activities aimed at specific objectives of the National Education Standards Institute (BSNP, 2006). In line with this, Saylor et al (1981: 3, cited in Suprijadi, 2008) point out that the curriculum refers to a plan to provide a series of learning opportunities for people who will be educated. This suggests that the curriculum is clearly very important in the teaching and learning process because it can guide teachers to be able to achieve educational goals.

According to Sukmadinata (2000, see Susilo, 2008: 9) that the curriculum is the core of the whole educational process because it becomes a guide to achieve educational goals. Thus, the curriculum is defined as a set of plans and rules about the objectives, content, and learning materials as well as how to use them as guidelines for implementing learning activities aimed at specific objectives of the National Standard of Institutional Education (BSNP, 2006). This shows that the curriculum contains a set of things that are explicit and implicit. The implicit intent is related to facilitating teaching and learning activities and their development (Miller and Seller, 1985). Thus, it can be said that the curriculum determines the success of the education system.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Since the direction, substance, and method of instruction eventually determine the kind and qualifications of graduates from an educational institution, the curriculum plays a crucial role in education (Uliatunida, N. 2020). Within a learning environment, one of the key players in developing the curriculum is the instructor. Teachers are the driving force behind educational achievement because they are directly involved in creating, supervising, and executing the curriculum to ensure that learning proceeds as planned and that the desired outcomes are met (Hasibuan, R.P. 2017). Despite how quickly science has advanced, this does not imply that teaching is becoming less important. Even the results of these technologies will increase the burden of the duties and responsibilities of teachers. Therefore, teachers as the main actors of education are required to fulfill their duties as curriculum developers and, of course, as professionals in education. The process of organizing the curriculum to create a comprehensive and detailed curriculum plan is known as curriculum development. This process involves choosing and setting up different elements of the teaching and learning environment, such as creating a schedule for curriculum structure and specification of suggested objectives, subjects, activities, resources, and measuring instruments.

METHODOLOGY

In this study the authors used library research methods. According to Mestika Zed, M (2008) the library method is a series of activities related to library data collection methods, reading, recording, and processing research materials. The library method relies on research materials from libraries such as books, journals, encyclopedias or magazines as data sources. Non-print works such as audio, video, and film recordings are also included as sources of library data. The results of the research are descriptive data in the form of speech or writing containing observations of people's behavior in a certain context studied from a whole, comprehensive, and holistic point of view.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Definition of Curriculum

The term curriculum comes from Latin, namely "curriculae", meaning the distance that must be traveled by a student, so the definition curriculum is an instructional program designed to instruct pupils through a variety of learning activities so that they can make adjustments and progress in their behavior occur, students with educational and learning goals. In other words, schools provide students with learning opportunities. That is why, a curriculum must be structured in such a way that this intention can be achieved. The curriculum is not limited to a number of subjects, but includes everything that can affect the development of students, such as: school buildings, learning tools, equipment, libraries, pictures, school grounds, and others. Which in turn provides the possibility of effective learning.

Curriculum has a very broad understanding, ranging from a limited attempt to influence students to learn inside and outside the classroom, to a broad understanding in which curriculum also includes educational facilities and infrastructure, students and even members of the community who have to make the educational process implemented (Suradnya 2009, p. 162).

The Concept of Curriculum Development in Learning

The curriculum is defined as *manhaj*, which is a light, or a light path that humans pass through in their field of life. While the curriculum in the context of education, means a bright path traveled by teachers with students to develop knowledge, skills and attitudes and values (Hasan Baharun 2017, p. 89-90). Meanwhile, according to Taba in Nasution interprets the curriculum as a "learning plan", which is planned for children's learning. The traditional view of the curriculum, formulates that the curriculum is a number of subjects that students must take to get a diploma (Lazwardi 2017, p. 101). Curriculum has a very broad understanding, ranging from a limited attempt to influence students to learn inside and outside the classroom, to a broad understanding where curriculum also includes educational facilities and infrastructure, students and even community members who must carry out the educational process in implementation.

The most common definition of curriculum is a set of subjects to be taught to students. The concept of curriculum as a learning experience better describes the situation more accurately than other concepts. Schools are established to

educate students, i.e. that they develop according to a certain path. Curriculum as a blueprint for education should lead to the provision of learning experiences for students that are well designed and properly implemented. Curriculum is also often defined as the subject matter or course material for learners, or lesson plans. Whether it is a plan, a document, or a learning guide, or a learning experience adopted by an individual, it will direct him or her in conducting learning activities (Lase 2018, p. 49-50). The curriculum plays a crucial role in the entire process of education. Curriculum theory evolves in tandem with educational theory and practice, and it also differs based on the educational theory or flow. As a result, the curriculum's organized learning experiences must take into account the demands of society (Fitrah 2015, p. 42-50). This is the process of curriculum planning to create a comprehensive and understandable curriculum plan in the context of curriculum development. The process involves choosing and setting up different elements of the teaching-learning environment, such as creating a schedule for curriculum management and deciding on the goals, topics, activities, resources, and metrics of curriculum development, which allude to the production of resources and unit plans and other lesson routes covering different areas of the curriculum to help with learning (Yu'timaalahuyatazaka 2016, p. 140). The word "curriculum development" is broad and encompasses planning, carrying out, and assessing. The first stage of developing a curriculum is called curriculum planning, during which curriculum specialists decide what to do and how to do it in order to create a plan that both instructors and students will use.

Principles of Curriculum Development in Improving Learning Quality

The process of developing a curriculum either creates new principles or applies ones that have evolved through daily life. Therefore, it is feasible to apply various principles from the curriculum used in other educational institutions while implementing the curriculum in educational institutions., so there will be many principles used in curriculum development (Fitroh 2011, p. 1-7). Sukmadinata states that the principles of curriculum development are divided into two types, namely general principles and specific principles. The general principles of curriculum development are relevance, flexibility, continuity, practicality and effectiveness. These principles are a strong landscape for realizing a curriculum that suits the needs of students, teachers and society. Specific principles of curriculum development are related to educational objectives, principles related to the selection of educational content, principles related to the selection of teaching and learning processes, principles related to the selection of media and learning tools, and principles related to the selection of assessment activities. The same thing stated by Hernawan in Sudrajat suggests five principles in curriculum development, namely:

1. Principle of relevance

Internally, the curriculum has relevance between curriculum components (objectives, materials, strategies, organization, and evaluation). While externally the components have relevance to the demands of science and technology (epistemological relevance), the demands and potential of students (psychological relevance), as well as the demands and needs of community

development (sociological relevance), so In order to prepare students for the workforce, the curriculum must take into account the demands of both the students and the surrounding community. to come. In reality, the above principles must really be considered because it will affect the quality of education. And last but not least, it must be in accordance with technological developments so that they are in line with efforts to build the country (Asmariyani 2014, p. 60).

2. The principle of flexibility

Curriculum development seeks to make the results flexible, flexible, and flexible in its implementation, allowing adjustments based on the situation and conditions of place and time that are always evolving, as well as the abilities and backgrounds of students, Since this adaptable principle must be seriously taken into consideration as a support for raising the standard of education, the curriculum plays a crucial role in the development of pupils in this situation. It is planned that the curriculum have flexibility under this principle of flexibility. A curriculum that includes strong content is considered to be good., However, in terms of execution, modifications can be made according to local circumstances, children's backgrounds and skills, and time constraints. Children are prepared for both the present and the future by this program. Everywhere the curriculum is still adaptable, curriculum development is still possible, especially for kids with diverse backgrounds and skill levels. The curriculum needs to give teachers the flexibility to create their own lesson plans. In this instance, educators have the power to create a curriculum that meets the needs of their academic field, students' interests, and both (Mansur 2016, p. 3).

The principle of continuity

The curriculum's emphasis on continuity must be applied to the learning process, both within grade levels and between educational levels as well as between different sorts of work and educational levels. Here, continuity refers to the importance of the connections between the curricula at different educational levels. in order to prevent learning materials from becoming monotonous or repetitive, which would bore both students and teachers, and cause them to get saturated. A flexible curriculum, on the other hand, is one that is not designed to be inflexible and allows instructors and students to freely select courses or learning resources, eliminating any possibility of coercion in the learning process. instruction (Zainab 2017, p. 366).

The principle of efficiency

The role of the curriculum in the realm of education is very important and even vital in the learning process, it covers everything in learning planning to be more optimal and effective. Today, the world of the industrial revolution offers a wide variety of curriculum developments born by experts from the western world. One of the curriculum developments used by the Indonesian government to achieve a national ideal is to optimize the intelligence of the nation's next generation of children to have noble akhlaq and noble character. One of the concepts that must be taken into account when creating the curriculum is efficiency, so that the planned content will match the desired outcomes. It is not a barrier if a learning program can be conducted one month at a time and

accomplish all of the goals established. In order for students to carry out other learning programs, efforts must be made in order for curriculum developers to best, carefully, and accurately use the educational resources already in place in order to provide outcomes that are adequate.

Principle of effectiveness

When creating a curriculum for education, the concept of effectiveness must be taken into account. Here, effectiveness refers to how well the learning program plan is carried out or accomplished. There are two parts of this principle that must be taken into account: the quality of the teacher's instruction and the effectiveness of the students' learning. If teachers continue to be less effective at imparting knowledge through programs or materials, this will be taken into consideration when designing the curriculum in the future through activities like workshops and training sessions. When it comes to the effectiveness of student learning, a curriculum pertaining to learning methodology must be created so that planned outcomes can be realized using instructional strategies that are appropriate for the subject matter. Thus, efforts are made to ensure that curriculum development activities meet objectives without engaging in an excessive amount of activity in terms of both quality and quantity. The goal of this curriculum creation is to enhance the quality of learning that is expected by all parties, particularly the efficacy of learning in the classroom, through its implementation in the learning process.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to Sukmadinata (2000, see Susilo, 2008: 9) that the curriculum is the core of the entire educational process because it is a guide to achieve educational goals. Thus, the curriculum is defined as a set of plans and rules about the objectives, content, and learning materials as well as how to use them as guidelines for implementing learning activities aimed at specific objectives of the National Standard of Institutional Education (BSNP, 2006). The principles of the curriculum include: the principle of relevance, the principle of flexibility, the principle of continuity, the principle of efficiency and the principle of effectiveness.

In order for curriculum development to succeed in accordance with what is desired, curriculum development requires a foundation of curriculum development. The foundation of curriculum development includes: Philosophical foundations, social, cultural and religious foundations, foundations of science, technology, and art, foundations of community needs, and foundations of community development.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Principles of Curriculum Development in an Effort to Improve Learning Quality in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

REFERENCES

- Asmariyani, A. (2014). Prinsip-Prinsip Pengembangan Kurikulum Dalam Perspektif Islam. *Al-Afkar: Jurnal Keislaman & Peradaban*, 2(2).
- Baharun, H. (2017). Peningkatan kompetensi guru melalui sistem kepemimpinan kepala madrasah. *At-Tajdid: Jurnal Ilmu Tarbiyah*, 6 (1), 1-26.
- Dimiyati dan Mudjiono, (2013). *Belajar dan Pembelajaran*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- Hamalik, O. (2002). *Pendidikan Guru Berdasarkan Pendekatan Kompetensi*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- Hasibuan, R. P. (2017). *Peran guru dalam pendidikan*.
- Lase, Famahato. 2018. "Dasar Pengembangan Kurikulum Menjadi Pengalaman Belajar." *Jurnal PG-PAUD STKIP Pahlawan Tuanku Tambusai* 3(1): 49-50.
- Lazwardi, D. (2017). Manajemen kurikulum sebagai pengembangan tujuan pendidikan. *Al-Idarah: Jurnal Kependidikan Islam*, 7(1), 119-125.
- Mansur, Rosichin. 2016. "Pengembangan Kurikulum Pendidikan Agama Islam Multikultural (Suatu Prinsip-Prinsip Pengembangan)." *Jurnal Ilmiah Vicratina* 10(2): 3.
- Oemar hamalik, (2012). *Manajemen Pengembangan Kurikulum*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya
- Oemar hamalik, (2019). *Kurikulum dan pembelajaran*. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
- Pranata, J., & Wijoyo, H. (2020, November). Analisis Upaya Mengembangkan Kurikulum Sekolah Minggu Buddha (SMB) Taman Lumbini Tebango Lombok Utara. In *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Pendidikan* (Vol. 2, pp. 778-786).
- Shofiyah, S. (2018). Prinsip- prinsip pengembangan kurikulum dalam upaya meningkatkan kualitas pembelajaran. *EDURELIGIA: Jurnal Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 2 (2), 122-130.
- Susilo, Jimat. 2016. "Pengembangan Kurikulum Bahasa Indonesia Bagi Penutur Asing." *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia* 3(1): 46
- Triwiyanto, T. (2022). *Manajemen kurikulum dan pembelajaran*. Bumi Aksara.
- Uliatunida, N. (2020). Perencanaan kurikulum untuk mencapai tujuan pendidikan. *Medikom | Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan dan Dakwah*, 2(1), 35-48.

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Yu'timaalahuyatazaka. 2016. "Model Pengembangan Kurikulum Hilda Taba dan Identifikasinya dalam Kurikulum Pendidikan Islam." *Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam* 4(2): 140

Zainab, Nurul. 2017. "Prinsip - Prinsip Pengembangan Kurikulum Pendidikan Agama Islam Perspektif Islam." *Jurnal Fenomena* 16(2): 366.

Zed, M. (2008). *Metode penelitian kepustakaan*. Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia.